

D8.2: Interim Dissemination Report

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable presents and updates the dissemination strategy for the 3D-ICONS project for year 3 of the project and provides a monitoring report on dissemination activities during years one and two.

The mission of the 3D-ICONS project is to raise awareness amongst archaeology and architecture content holders of the positive conditions for making content available to Europeana, and to give a persuasive demonstration of best practices to promote use of the project's results by the wider community.

The aims of the dissemination strategy continue to be raising awareness about the 3D-ICONS project and 3D digitisation amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations,
- External stakeholders: Organisations with an interest in 3D digitisation including Europeana, cultural heritage institutions, academic institutions, commercial enterprises and others,
- The Research Community,
- European Commission's CIP ICT PSP and Horizon 2020 programmes: directors, project officers and related projects.

The objectives of the dissemination strategy are to:

- Define the stakeholder community, identify its interests and the main channels for communication and networking activities,
- Build and extend the contact database by clustering with other projects, participation in events and exploiting the partners' networks of contacts,
- Informing the stakeholder community about news, events and activities by developing a project newsletter, exploiting social networking channels as well as traditional media,
- Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials by developing the project website, a brochure and other materials for use by the partners,
- Presenting the project at relevant national and international events.

Monitoring of the project's dissemination activity during the first two years of the project showed that the targets set at the start of the project have been met and most have been exceeded:

- More than two international events have been organised,
- Partners have delivered more than 26 presentations at international conferences,
- 27 articles have been published in conference proceedings and academic journals,
- The project website has received more than 12,500 visits,
- Project news and the newsletter are being read by more than 200 people,
- The project has established external partner agreements with four organisations.

2. Dissemination strategy

3D-ICONS is co-funded by the European Commission ICT PSP programme. The project started on the 1st February 2012 and runs for three years. It brings together partners from across Europe with the relevant expertise to digitise architectural and archaeological monuments and buildings in 3D and is designed to:

- establish a complete pipeline for the production of 3D replicas of archaeological monuments and historic buildings which covers all technical, legal and organisational aspects;
- create 3D models and a range of other materials (images, texts and videos) of a series of internationally important monuments and buildings; and
- contribute content to Europeana using the CARARE aggregation service.

The aim of WP8 (dissemination) is to develop the consortium's strategy for effective dissemination of the project's results in the culture sector business environment and the academic world, its achievements in digitising archaeology/architecture content and preparing 3D models and to raise awareness and transfer knowledge.

The aim of the dissemination strategy is to raise awareness about the 3D-ICONS project and 3D digitisation amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations,
- External stakeholders: Organisations with an interest in 3D digitisation including Europeana, cultural heritage institutions, academic institutions, commercial enterprises and others.
- The Research Community,
- European Commission's CIP ICT PSP and Horizon 2020 programme: directors, project officers and related projects funded by the programme.

The dissemination strategy was prepared by MDR Partners during the first six months of the project and is updated in this deliverable ([2] sets out the initial strategy). This dissemination strategy for the project aims to:

- Define appropriate **messages** targeted to specific audiences,
- Define appropriate **materials** targeted to specific audiences,
- Define the **timeline** for dissemination activities,
- Identify **resources** to be devoted to dissemination activities,
- Define partner responsibilities for **tasks**,
- Define the information **workflow**,
- Establish the Stakeholder **contact database**,
- Provide qualitative and quantitative **indicators and targets**.

We have identified 5 main objectives for the dissemination strategy and corresponding activities for the coming period (Table 1):

Objective	Description	2013-14 activity
Objective 1	Defining the stakeholder business and operational considerations	Continuing to identify channels of communication and possible networking activities and: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying the communities interests and understanding of operational considerations Exploring and developing business models relevant to stakeholders
Objective 2	Building and extending the contact database	Maximising contacts through partners networks to disseminate news Continuing to build a network of followers in Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn to share and exchange news about relevant activities Continuing clustering with other projects Participation in events
Objective 3	Informing the stakeholder community about news, events and activities	3 issues of the Project Newsletter Continued use of Mailing lists and Social Networks to disseminate news and to drive traffic to the project websites. Press Notices – project activities Call for participation in the project’s final event
Objective 4	Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials	Updating the Project Website with reports, publications and other materials. 3D-ICONS publication Project poster Project video
Objective 5	Presenting the project at relevant national and international events	Participation in relevant events to present 3D-ICONS project results 3D-ICONS final event

Table 1: Dissemination strategy

3. Defining the stakeholder community

As a 3D digitisation project, 3D-ICONS is implementing techniques, developing guidelines and business models aimed to be suitable for institutions involved in cultural heritage digitisation projects. The project has identified different stakeholder groups with an interest in its activities. Different approaches are appropriate to the different groups, for example, different mailing lists or conferences may be used. By defining the stakeholder community our aim is to make our dissemination activities more relevant to the people and organisations involved.

The 3D-ICONS stakeholder community includes:

- Internal stakeholders in 3D-ICONS partner institutions who have an interest or involvement in 3D digitisation and/or the archaeological and architectural heritage; institutions which have signed an external partner agreement with 3D-ICONS;
- UNESCO and cultural institutions with responsibilities for internationally and nationally important monuments and buildings interested in finding new ways of delivering their missions to promote understanding and increase the sustainability of this heritage, and with an interest in tried and tested mechanisms to produce high quality 3D documentation and publish the results online;
- Research community and creative industry SMEs with an interest and involvement in producing high quality 3D documentation of the archaeological and architectural heritage;
- The European Commission and its digital content programmes;
- Europeana, members of the general public, tourists and students who wish to be able to use 3D content to explore and enjoy architectural and archaeological masterpieces.

3.1 Internal stakeholders

Internal stakeholders are one of the target audiences for the 3D-ICONS project as it is important to keep policy makers and staff within partner organisations aware of the project's activities and results, and to encourage them to share news with their contacts.

Staff within the partner institutions may be interested in news about:

- Digitisation of specific monuments and buildings,
- The use of particular technologies,
- Standards and guidelines,
- Releases of new content in Europeana,
- Conferences and other events,
- Business models.

This group includes organisations which are external to the 3D-ICONS project consortium but which expressed interest in providing content to Europeana via 3D-ICONS and have signed **external partner agreements** with the project.

The aim of this dissemination activity is to make the subjects aware about 3D-ICONS and its activities and to spread the news to their contacts.

Internal stakeholders will be reached during internal meetings through presentations of the project activities and dissemination of news.

3.2 UNESCO and Cultural institutions

UNESCO and cultural heritage institutions involved in the Europeana Network form an important dissemination target for the project. These are institutions with responsibilities for the management, protection and understanding of internationally and nationally important monuments and buildings who in many cases also have an interest in using new technologies for documentation and presentation purposes.

Staff within these institutions may be interested in news about:

- Digitisation of specific monuments and buildings,
- The technologies and services,
- Standards and guidelines,
- Releases of new content in Europeana,
- Conferences and other events,
- Sustainable business models.

3D-ICONS will interact with this stakeholder community by participating in conferences and events, organising workshops, making use of social channels, by disseminating news and by making materials available on the project website.

3.3 Research community and Creative industry SMEs

This is the community of researchers and creative industry SMEs who are active in the field of 3D documentation of the cultural heritage, and in particular archaeological monuments and historical buildings.

The community is likely to be interested in:

- Specific research outcomes,
- The technologies being used and their implementation in specific projects,
- Standards and guidelines,
- Business models,
- Needs and requirements of the cultural heritage institutions,
- Participation in conferences and events.

3D-ICONS will interact with this stakeholder community by participating in conferences and events, organising workshops, making use of social channels, by disseminating news and by making materials available on the project website.

3.4 European Commission

The European Commission is an important stakeholder in the outcomes of the 3D-ICONS project and represents both an opportunity to disseminate project outcomes to policy makers and also provides dissemination channels to related projects funded by the programme.

The European Commission, its staff and news channels are likely to be interested in news about:

- Digitisation of specific monuments and buildings,
- The results and outcomes of the project,
- Delivery of content to Europeana,
- Standards and guidelines,
- Evaluation of the results.

The 3D-ICONS project will aim to take advantage of opportunities to present the outcomes at **events** organised by the European Commission spread the word about 3D documentation of cultural heritage sites. The 3D-ICONS team will take part in collaboration events organised by the EC to share results with other funded projects. These will be also reached through direct contacts, participation in international events and other dissemination channels (see section **Error! Reference source not found.**).

The project **newsletter** and other news items will be distributed to the project officer via email and twitter.

3D-ICONS project will aim to contribute to showing the success of the EC Programmes and initiatives by demonstrating the important progress being made in the direction of accessing, using and sharing cultural heritage resources in ways which adapt to user needs.

4. Identifying resources

This section identifies the skills and experiences available within the project consortium and their connections with projects, networks and associations.

4.1 Consortium

The dissemination work package is lead by MDR and which involves all partners in the project consortium with the sole exception of NTUA.

The 3D-ICONS consortium consists of 16 partners in 10 countries including Italy, United Kingdom, Greece, Ireland, Spain, Belgium, France, Cyprus and Romania.

All project partners are responsible for contributing to dissemination activities including the identification of events, development of dissemination materials and to the development of the project website. Most of the partners have public relations departments in their institutions, or access to external resources, on which to draw relevant skills and experience for marketing 3D-ICONS.

Responsibilities for dissemination activities:

- CISA and MDR together have strategic responsibility for coordinating dissemination activities by all partners,
- MDR is responsible for coordinating the development of the project website and for providing a set of dissemination materials,
- KMKG is responsible for coordinating the dissemination of news and information about the project through Twitter, Facebook and the project newsletter,
- STARC was responsible for organising a workshop at an international conference during year one of the project,
- DISC was responsible for organising a workshop at an international conference during year two,
- CISA is responsible for organising a conference during the final year of the project supported by MDR,
- All partners are responsible for disseminating about the project at conferences, events, workshops and via news and social media,
- All partners are responsible for naming a dissemination lead person who will be responsible for reporting on dissemination activities and for contributing to the development of the project dissemination plan, etc.

4.2 Clustering with other projects

3D-ICONS has identified a number of projects who are active within its field. These projects represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for 3D-ICONS will be to approach the projects offering to exchange news about project activities and to seek opportunities for collaboration.

The projects which been identified include:

- CARARE¹ (stakeholder community: cultural institutions)
- 3D-COFORM² (stakeholder community: researchers)
- V-MUST³ (stakeholder community: researchers and creative SMEs)
- Scottish Ten⁴ (stakeholder community: researchers and creative SMEs)
- Partage Plus⁵ (stakeholder community: museums)
- Europeana⁶ (stakeholder community: cultural institutions)
- ARIADNE⁷ (stakeholder community: researchers)

3D-ICONS is a member of the Europeana group of projects and is represented by MDR in the Europeana communications group. The Europeana office maintains the Europeana Pro website (<http://pro.europeana.eu/>) and disseminates information about projects, including 3D-ICONS, to its stakeholder community through the website, a quarterly newsletter, its blog and other news channels. The office also maintains a calendar of events informing group members about upcoming events, inviting participation in clustering activities and disseminating information about project’s participation in international conferences and events

The 3D-ICONS team will follow the projects identified above via their websites, Twitter and the other social networks.

The aim will be to coordinate the approaches to the projects identified to avoid duplication and to maximum effect. The table below identified which PARTNER will contact specific projects, WHEN contact will be made and WHAT the nature of the contact will be (e.g. to discuss collaboration or partner opportunities, exchange news, etc.).

Project	Partner to contact	When	Nature of the contact
CARARE	MDR	Now	Collaboration
ARIADNE	MDR	Now	Exchange news
3D-COFORM	CISA	Now	Collaboration

¹ <http://www.carare.eu>

² <http://www.3d-coform.eu/>

³ <http://www.v-must.net/>

⁴ <http://www.scottishten.org/>

⁵ <http://www.partage-plus.eu/>

⁶ <http://pro.europeana.eu>

⁷ <http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Scottish Ten	Discovery	Now	Exchange news
V-MUST	Visual Dimension	Now	Collaboration
Europeana Photography	MDR	Now	Liaise for dissemination

4.3 Groups and associations

Several 3D-ICONS partners are members of groups and associations that are active within the field. These groups and associations each represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for 3D-ICONS will be to explore opportunities to dissemination news and information about project activities with these groups.

The groups and associations identified include:

- 3dheritage.org
- Computer Applications in Archaeology (CAA)
- European Association of Archaeologists (EAA)
- Irish Institute of Surveyors (IIS)
- Aerial Archaeology Research Group (AARG)
- International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (ISPRS)
- European Association of Remote Sensing Laboratories (EARsel)
- Network TechnoHeritage: Red de Ciencia y Tecnología para la Conservación del Patrimonio Cultural (Science and Technology for conservation of Cultural Heritage)

4.4 Stakeholder database

The objective for 2014 will be to build the project’s contact database by encouraging subscriptions to the project newsletter, followers on Twitter and membership of the project’s Facebook group. The target for 2014 will be to increase the current following on social networks as follows:

- Twitter increase from 150 to 300 followers
- Facebook increase from 82 to 150 members
- LinkedIn (CARARE group) 597 to 650 members

The strategies for building and extending the contact database include clustering with other projects, disseminating news and updates about the project’s activities through various channels including direct contacts of partners’ network, use of social media, project newsletter, press notices (see section 5) and by participating in conferences and events (see section 7).

5. Informing the stakeholder community

Our objective is to inform the stakeholder community about news, events and project activities. This will be done through the different channels (project newsletter, mailing lists, social networks, press notices) documented below.

Our strategy is to approach the target audience by making use of social media, professional/personal/local contacts from the project partners' network, etc.

Contacts will be made through the use of an appropriate **message** to transmit information that can vary according to the target audience. For example, when reaching the research community we could point out specific academic 3D-ICONS publications on the project website or news about forthcoming conferences.

During 2014 the programme of work by partners to capture archaeological and architectural monuments in 3D will be some of the achievements to inform our stakeholder community about.

5.1 Mailing lists

The members of the project team are each registered on various mailing lists for professional reasons. These lists cover different subjects in the Cultural heritage, research and business domains and have different memberships.

The project is creating a document summarising the email lists that each team member will be responsible for circulating project news to. Partners have been asked to identify which email lists team members are signed up to. A master list will then be made and MDR and KMKG will coordinate the dissemination of news items to the lists, with the aim of guaranteeing coverage and avoiding duplication.

The strategy is to post notices about 3D-ICONS to the lists (for example the newsletter or a forthcoming event with a link to the project website). Such notices are a good way of driving traffic to the website and allow contacts the opportunity of registering to receive a copy of the Newsletter directly.

The work of sending notices will be done periodically according to the project activities and developments.

The emailing lists that have been identified include:

- HERITAGE
- DIGITAL-CULTURE
- JISC-E-COLLECTIONS
- JISCDIGITALMEDIA
- MUSEUMS-INFO

- MUSEUMINFO-RECORDS
- ARTS-HERITAGE-MARKETING

5.2 Social networks

Twitter

The strategy for **Twitter**⁸ during 2014 will be to:

- Post Tweets related to the project's activities (Newsletter, events, project progresses) or information related to domains of interest to 3D-ICONS. This will keep followers informed about the project and activate new discussions around pertinent areas.
- Encourage the partners to share interesting news and then retweet their messages.
- Monitor events (who's attending what events) and tweet about the event with the event hashtag
- Involve 3D-ICONS project members who are active on Twitter to create interest around 3D-ICONS by Tweeting about the project using @3DIcons and to retweet notices from the project twitter account to their followers.
- Include the project Twitter feed on the home page of the project website.
- Integrate Twitter with Facebook. Tweets will be automatically re-posted onto LinkedIn: this mechanism will ensure a consistent flow of information and will populate the social networks.
- Follow lists of relevant Twitter users. This activity give the 3D-ICONS project visibility: using retweets with @Twitter_user (or #FF Twitter_users on Fridays) to build 3D-ICONS's profile and encourage others to return the favour by retweeting 3D-ICONS tweets to their followers etc.

Currently 3D-ICONS is following 162 Twitter users including:

- @ScottishTen
- @FutureLab3D – robotics, 3D printing etc
- @V_MUST
- @Laserscanningeu - Laser scanning Europe
- @lidarnews – Gene Roe
- @UNESCOheritage – UNESCO
- @NottinghamCaves – Nottingham Cave Surveys
- @nextengine – Nextengine

In order to make the best use of Twitter a document containing Guidelines for Tweeting about the 3D-ICONS Project has been created (see

⁸ <http://www.twitter.com/3Dicons>

Appendix I: Twitter Guidelines) and additional useful material on the use of Twitter has been circulated to partners on Basecamp.

LinkedIn

The strategy for **LinkedIn** during 2013 was to merge the 3D-ICONS LinkedIn group with the existing group established by the CARARE project. The strategy for 2014 will be to promote discussion about 3D digitisation and about project activities. The objective will be to increase the number of followers of the group during the year.

The group can be found at:

http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=2792030&trk=anet_ug_hm

Our strategy will be to involve the members in discussions around the project.

Among the list of relevant LinkedIn groups for dissemination we identified:

- 3D-COFORM
- 3D Scanning / Reverse Engineering
- 3D Visualisation and Graphics Programming
- 3D Business
- ArchaeoLandscapes Europe
- Archeology
- CAA: Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology
- CIDOC - International Documentation Committee of ICOM
- Computer Vision Technologies
- Digital Heritage Preservation
- Geomatics
- Information Technologies and Cultural Heritage
- Laser Scanning
- Laser Scanning Forum
- The LiDAR Forum
- Open Source LiDAR
- Photogrammetry & Laser Scanning
- Spatial Ireland
- Web3D Professionals
- WebGL Developers

YouTube

A YouTube channel has been established for the project. The intention is to use this channel to publish videos about the project and its digitisation activities.

FaceBook

A Facebook group has been established for the project at:

<http://www.facebook.com/groups/127358380732567/>. This will be linked to the project Twitter feed, with the aim of disseminating news about the project's activities to as wide an audience as possible. Among the list of relevant Facebook pages we identified:

- CARARE
- 3D scanning of Cultural Heritage
- SCUOLA DI ARCHEOLOGIA VIRTUALE V-MUST
- MeshLab

Other media channels

Boletín Proyecto Campus de Excelencia Internacional en Patrimonio Cultural y Natural
(Newsletter International Excellence Campus about Cultural and Natural Heritage)

5.3 Press notices

Press notices and press release are an effective way to disseminate the project outcomes to news media: Newspapers or magazines (online or papers versions), news sites, news networks.

6. Dissemination materials

A set of dissemination materials has been produced for the project and will be updated during 2014 to reflect the final phase of the project.

6.1 Project logo

The project logo was designed by Carol Usher of MDR Partners.

6.2 Project website

The 3D-ICONS website (<http://www.3dicons-project.eu/>) will continue to offer information about the project and its partners, and to present the results of the project. Reports, presentations and papers by project partners are made available on the website along with news, information about events.

One of our objectives for 2014 is to increase the traffic on the website which will be done by disseminating news about new publications, news stories and newsletters via email marketing and the social networks.

The website is hosted and maintained by MDR and is made available in English.

6.3 Project newsletter

4 issues of the project newsletter have been produced and are available from: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Newsletter>. Newsletters are distributed by direct email to registered stakeholders, via the email distribution lists and also by sending out notices to followers on Twitter.

The project plans to produce 3 further issues of the newsletter during 2014. The editorial strategy will be to create articles talking about 3D-ICONS related topics including:

- project achievements
- events attended by the project Consortium
- partner profiles
- dynamic articles describing activities such as field work
- news from projects active in same area as 3D-ICONS

Newsletter #4

Welcome to the fourth issue of the 3D-Icons newsletter! 3D-ICONS is a project funded under the European Commission's ICT Policy Support Programme and will be using 3D techniques to digitise UNESCO World Heritage Sites and to provide content to Europeana. In this issue, besides updates on partners and events we highlight the **work in progress** in the project, both in front, scanning cultural heritage sites all over Europe, and in the background, the development of a new metadata model.

 [Friend on Facebook](#)

 [Follow on Twitter](#)

Upcoming events

[CHNT 2013](#)

Mon 11 Nov 10:00 - Wed 13 Nov 17:00

The 18th International Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies will be held in from 11-13th November 2013 in Vienna, Austria.

[Constructing vocabularies at a European level Reference lists, thesauri, and ontologies for Digital Humanities](#)

DARIAH-FR Workshop - Paris, 27th November 2013

6.4 Project video

A project show reel was produced by Discovery incorporating contributions of videos of 3D digitisation projects from several partners. The video was prepared for the exhibition at Digital Heritage 2013 and has now been uploaded to YouTube and incorporated into the project website on: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/Community>.

A new project video is planned for 2014.

6.5 Other dissemination materials

A set of promotional materials has been prepared and made available for use. These materials include:

- A selection of images made available by project partners for use in dissemination materials
- A project fact sheet and postcard
- A project poster
- A 3D-ICONS Essentials PowerPoint presentation.
- Templates for fact sheets, presentations etc.

3D-ICONS is digitising iconic monuments and buildings, many from World Heritage sites, to bring around 3,000 3D models to Europeana and its users.

The project will establish a processing pipeline from digitisation, post-processing, metadata and final output formats.

3D-ICONS is using the CARARE2 Metadata Schema which is specifically designed for archaeology and 3D models.

info@3dicons-project.eu

3D ICONS is funded by the European Commission's ICT Policy Support Programme

www.3dicons-project.eu

Project poster

These materials are made available to members of the project for download from the 3D-ICONS Intranet. Additional materials will be made available throughout the life of the project as needs are identified by the dissemination plan.

6.6 Acknowledgement of EU funding

Dissemination materials including reports, presentations, promotional material and publications must clearly acknowledge the EU funding through the inclusion of an appropriate statement and the EU flag.

Example: "This project is partially funded under the ICT Policy Support Programme (ICT PSP) as part of the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme by the European Community" (ideally with a link to the ICT PSP website: http://ec.europa.eu/ict_psp).

Any communication or publication shall state that it reflects only the author's views and that the European Community is not liable for any use that might be made of the information contained therein.

7. Dissemination activities

7.1 Conferences and events

3D-ICONS has been presented at a number of conferences and events since the project began.

Date	Event	Link
9-11 May 2012	EVA Florence, Florence, Italy Presentation and paper (CISA and MDR)	http://www.evaflorence.it/
13-15 June 2012	Europeana Plenary, Leuven Distributing postcards and networking (MDR)	http://pro.europeana.eu/web/leuven-2012
2-7 July 2012	3D Visualisation for the study and management of complex archaeological sites, summer school, Carnuntum, Austria Presentation (VisDim)	http://www2.radiopast.eu/wp-content/uploads/program-1.pdf
25 Aug – 1 Sept 2012	ISPRS Congress, Melbourne, Australia Presentation (FBK)	http://www.isprs.org/
29 Aug – 1 Sept 2012	CultureTECH, Derry/Londonderry, UK Presentation (DISC)	
29 Oct – 3 Nov 2012	EuroMed 2012 Conference, Limassol, Cyprus (FBK, MDR, CNRS)	http://www.euromed2012.eu/
2-5 Sept 2012	VSMM 2012, Milan, Italy (CISA, MDR, Polimi, FBK, CNRS, VisDim)	http://www.vsmm2012.org/
25 Sept 2012	Presentations at KOREC Surveying Roadshow in Cork, Ireland (DISC)	
2 Oct 2012	Presentations at KOREC Surveying Roadshow in Belfast, UK (DISC)	
30 Oct 2012	Opening of “Reshaping history exhibition” at the Museo Archeologico Nazionale, Naples	

	Presentation (CISA)	
21 Nov 2012	VAST 2012, Brighton UK – 3D-ICONS workshop (CISA, MDR, CNR ISTI, CMC)	http://www.vast2012.org/
11 Dec 2012	Presentation to ICOMOS Ireland at the Royal Society of Antiquities Ireland (DISC)	
16 Jan 2013	Radio-Past Colloquium, Ghent, Belgium Presentation (DISC, VisDim)	http://www2.radiopast.eu/?page_id=2332
13 Apr 2013	Rathcroghan Archaeological Conference 2013, Ireland, Presentation (DISC)	http://www.rathcroghanconference.com/
May 2013	“Aggregating and promoting Visual cultural content”, Presentation at the annual meeting of the Union of Archaeologists, Plaka, Athens, Greece (NTUA)	
15 May 2013	Korec Technology Day 2013, Maynooth, Ireland, Presentation (DISC)	
15 May 2013	EVA Florence, Prato workshop, Paper on new technologies (CMD)	http://www.evaflorence.it/
20 May 2013	Presentation of first project results to a general public audience and media including Radio România Cultural (MNIR)	
27-30 May 2013	Coordination and organisation of Virtual Heritage School 2013, The Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus (CYI-STARC org, contribs. by CNR-ITABC, CNR-ISTI, POLIMI)	http://www.v-must.net/schoolscyprus-virtual-heritage-school-2013
28 May 2013	Korec Technology Day 2013, Belfast, UK, Presentation (DISC)	
29 May 2013	Patrimonium International Symposium, Alba Iulia, presentation (MNIR)	

30 May 2013	Round the World Symposium, Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland, Presentation (DISC)	http://kuleinstitute.wordpress.com/2013/05/
14-16 June 2013	Opening the past 2013, Pisa, Italy, Presentation (CISA)	http://mappaproject.arch.unipi.it/?page_id=1739
16-22 June 2013	Summer school on 3D surveying and modelling, Paestum, Italy (FBK org., POLIMI contrib.)	http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/News-from-Paestum
27-8 June 2013	Cultural Heritage, Creative Tools and Archives Workshop, Copenhagen, Denmark, Presentation (MNIR)	
1-3 July 2013	International conference on digital signal processing (DSP'13), Santorini, Greece Presentation (NTUA)	http://dsp2013.dspconferences.org/
5 July 2013	Digital Heritage 2013: Interfaces with the Past, University of York, UK, Poster (DISC)	http://www.york.ac.uk/digital-heritage/events/cdh-2013/
17 July 2013	Hill of Tara Annual Summer Lectures, Meath, Ireland (DISC)	
22 Aug 2013	Photogrammetry workshop, Romania (MNIR)	http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/MNIR-workshop
24 Aug 2013	Heritage Week 2013, Royal Society of Ireland (DISC)	http://www.discoveryprogramme.ie/news-a-events/news/218-dprsai-heritage-week-event-this-saturday-24-august.html
30 Aug 2013	3D Agora meeting Tervuren, Belgium, Presentation Networking (KMKG, VisDim)	http://agora3d.africamuseum.be/
1-2 Sept 2013	IANUS-DARIAH IPR workshop, Berlin, Germany (MDR)	https://de.dariah.eu/en/methoden-workshops
2-6 Sept 2013	CIPA Symposium, Strasbourg, France (FBK, POLIMI, CNRS)	http://cipa.icomos.org/
20-26	Summer school "Drones	http://www.v-must.net/activities/international-

Sept 2013	applied to Cultural Heritage and Archaeology”, Pontignano, Italy (FBK, CNRS, CNR)	summer-school-drones-applied-cultural-heritage-and-archaeology
26 Sept 2013	Aerial Archaeology Research Group (AARG) Conference, Amersfoort, Netherlands, Presentation (DISC)	http://www.decars.nl/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=124&Itemid=76&lang=en
10 Oct 2013	eChallenges e-2013 Conference, Dublin, Ireland, Presentation (DISC)	http://www.echallenges.org/e2013/
16-18 Oct 2013	3D-Doc. in Archaeology & Monument Preservation, held at LWL Industrial Museum, Dortmund, Germany (MNIR)	http://www.denkmaeler3.de/English/index-en.html
24 Oct 2013	European Walled Towns Symposium, Derry, UK, Presentation (DISC)	http://walls400.com/symposium/
24 Oct 2013	Scientific Support for Growth & Jobs: Cultural and Creative Industries Brussels, Belgium, posters and presentation (CYI-STARC)	http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/jrc/index.cfm?id=1410&obj_id=4700&dt_code=EVN&lang=en
28 Oct - 01 Nov 2013	Digital Heritage International Congress 2013, Marseille, France, Presentations and project workshop (CNRS conf org, DISC workshop org, contribs by CNR, CYI-STARC, FBK, POLIMI, VisDim, UJA-CAAI, MDR) networking (KMKG)	http://www.digitalheritage2013.org/
13 Nov 2013	SPAR Europe Conference, Amsterdam, Netherlands, Presentation (DISC)	http://www.sparpointgroup.com/Europe/
18 - 30 Nov 2013	Built Heritage 2013 – Monitoring Conservation Management, Milan, Italy, Presentation (CISA, CYI-STARC)	http://bh2013.polimi.it/
27-29 Nov 2013	Virtual Retrospect 2013, Bordeaux, France (contrib by Archeotransfert)	http://archeovision.cnrs.fr/spip.php?rubrique41
2 Dec	Europeana plenary meeting,	

2013	Networking (CISA, MDR, KMKG)	
3-6 Dec 2013	International Conference on Computer Vision, ICCV, Sydney, Australia Paper (NTUA)	http://www.iccv2013.org/
16 Jan 2014	U3A Scotland, Paper on Scara Brae Survey (CMC)	

7.2 Potential conferences and events: 2014

Partners have identified the following conferences and events as being of potential interest to the project in 2014.

Date	Event	Link
2 Feb 2014	SPIE: IS&T/SPIE Imaging 2014	http://spie.org/x16218.xml?WT.mc_id=REI14GB
12-14 Feb 2014	Digital Past 2014, Llandudno, UK New technologies in heritage, interpretation and outreach	http://www.rcahmw.gov.uk/HI/ENG/Our+Services/Outreach+/
19-21 Feb 2014	MWF2014: Museums and the Web Florence 2014	http://mwf2014.museumsandtheweb.com/
24 Feb 2014	PATCH2014 Workshop 7th International Workshop on Personalized Access to Cultural Heritage	http://patch2014.wordpress.com/
7-8 Mar 2014	CAA-GR 2014 – conference of the Greek Chapter of CAA, Rethymnon, Greece	http://caa-gr.org/2014/
26 Mar 2014	TRAIL 2014: Training and Research in the Archaeological Interpretation of Lidar, Frasné, France	http://trail2014.univ-fcomte.fr
22 Apr 2014	CAA 2014: Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology, Paris, France	http://caa2014.sciencesconf.org/
27 Apr 2014	EGU 2014 – UAV session Unmanned aerial vehicles for high resolution remote sensing	http://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU2014/session/15488 http://www.egu2014.eu

	in the geosciences, Vienna Austria	
10 Jun 2014	CGI 2014 – Computing Graphics International, Sydney Australia	http://sydney.edu.au/engineering/it/~cgi14/welcome/index.php
19-21 Jun 2014	EAHN 2014 – European Architectural History Network	http://www.eahn2014.polito.it/
23-25 Jun 2014	ISPRS 2014, International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, Technical Commission Symposium, Riva del Garda, Italy	http://isprs-commission5.fbk.eu/
8 Jul 2014	LIDAR visualisation and interpretation workshop, Esslingen, Germany	
10-14 Sept 2014	EAA 2014: European Association of Archaeologists 20 th Annual meeting	https://www.eaa2014istanbul.org/site
17-20 Sept 2014	LAC 2014: 3 rd international landscape archaeology conference	http://www.knir.it/en/category-evenementen/576-3d-international-landscape-archaeology-conference.html
Sept 2014	International summer school: Photogrammetry applied to cultural heritage (MNIR)	
30-31 Oct – 1-2 Nov 2014	Mediterranean Exchange of Archaeological Tourism, Paestum, Italy	http://www.borsaturismoarcheologico.it/en/
Oct 2014	Multidisciplinary approaches for cultural heritage, International conference (MNIR)	
3 Nov 2014	EuroMed 2014 Cultural Heritage eDocumentation, Preservation and Protection	http://www.culturalheritage2014.eu/
13-16 Nov 2014	AR&PA Biennial on Heritage Restoration and Management, Valladolid, Spain	http://www.jcyl.es/arpa
Nov-Dec 2014	UJA-CAAI. National workshop in Jaén	

Nov-Dec 2014	UJA-CAAI. Final press conference showing the results of 3D-ICONS.	
Feb-March 2015	3D-Arch conference, Italy	http://www.3d-arch.org/

7.4 3D-ICONS international Workshops

2012 workshop

STARC organised the 3D-ICONS workshop within the framework of the VAST2012 International Congress in Brighton on November 21st 2012. The initiative was attended by 15 people from different countries.

After a short introduction given by Sheena Bassett (MDR) about the objectives of the project, the Workshop focused on metadata for 3D Models with the contributions of Andrea D'Andrea (CISA) and Kate Fernie (MDR). They were followed by Mike Spearman (CMC), who illustrated the preliminary report on IPR and business model. Finally, Marco Callieri (ISTI-CNR) gave a contribution about the 3D technologies for Cultural Heritage. The participants asked many questions and were genuinely engaged with the subject. It was also interesting to hear and to share about their practical experiences.

2013 workshop

DISC organised the “Exploring the 3D-Icons Project on Thursday October 31, 2013. The workshop was hosted at the Digital heritage International Congress 2013 in the spectacular surroundings of the newly built Museum of Civilisations from Europe and the Mediterranean (MuCEM) in Marseille, France. The workshop was designed to introduce the 3D-ICONS Project to the wider research community and explore the digitisation pipeline developed as part of the project. This pipeline exploits and integrates existing tools and methods that enable the capture, modelling description and publication of 3D cultural heritage content on the web. The project pipeline themes of capture, model, describe and publish also informed the structure for the workshop sessions to provide a narrative structure for the audience.

Several of the partners contributed to the workshop providing case studies of digitisation work in progress, on metadata capture, quality control, use and re-use of 3D models. (CISA, MDR, DISC, FBK, MAP, MNIR, VisDim, UJA-CAAI, CYI-STARC and Polimi). The workshop was attended by 29 participants.

2014 Final project event

A final project event will be organised by CISA and MDR during autumn 2014. The current plans are to organise a workshop, held alongside an international conference in the project subject domain. The possibility of holding the event at Paestum during the annual Mediterranean Exchange on Cultural Tourism is currently being investigated. The Paestum conference is attended by around 4,000 delegates and is being held this year on 1-2 November.

7.3 Publications

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D'Andrea, A., Niccolucci, F., Bassett, and Fernie, K., *'3D-ICONS: World Heritage Sites for Europeana: Making Complex 3D Models Available to Everyone'*, VSMM 2012.

D'Andrea, A., *'Provenance e Paradata negli OpenData: il modello 3D-ICONS'*, Opening the Past, Pisa, Italy, 14th-16th June 2013.

http://mappaproject.arch.unipi.it/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/OP2013_pre_atti_rid.pdf

D'Andrea, A., *Integrating Architectural and Archaeological 3D-Models into Europeana*, Newsletter di Archeologia CISA, Volume 3, 2012, pp. 87-109.

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In preparation

UJA-CAAI - Paper for the Journal of the Instituto Andaluz del Patrimonio Histórico (Andalusia Historical Heritage Institute). Journal: *PH Boletín del IAPH*. In preparation

7.4 Other activities

In March 2012, Daniel Pletinckx of Visual Dimension took part in an event to mark the official opening of the tourist season in the province of East Flanders, Zottegem, Belgium:

http://www.radiomfm.be/plugins/p2_news/printarticle.php?p2_articleid=2237

Press conference to launch 3D-ICONS project in Spain was held at the University of Jaén on the 21st May 2012: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/CAAI-launches-3D-ICONS>

Press conference about 3D-ICONS progress in Spain on July 11, 2013. Presentation of 3D models of Cerrillo Blanco, Porcuna, Jaen. <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/CAAI-presents-first-results>. The media who attended or published information were:

- Canal Sur Televisión (TV channel)
- Onda Jaén Televisión (TV channel)
- Ondaluz Televisión (TV channel)
- Viva Jaén (newspaper)
- Diario Jaén (newspaper)
- Diario Ideal (newspaper)
- Diario EL PAIS (newspaper)
- La Razón (newspaper)
- Cadena SER (radio channel) (interviewed Arturo Ruiz)
- Radio Nacional de España (interviewed Alberto Sánchez)

Special report of Jaen newspaper about 3D-ICONS and the Iberians. Section Campus.

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/127358380732567/>

Official Irish launch of 3D-ICONS project at the Royal Irish Academy, Dublin, Ireland 18th April 2012: <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/New-3D-Project>

Booth at VSMM2012 Milan, Italy, 2-5 September 2012, showing a general overview on the project, organized by Polimi. 3D-ICONS mentioned in the “Dissemination Partners” list:

http://www.vsmm2012.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=13&Itemid=124

Full page news item in *Archaeology Ireland* magazine, Winter Issue 2013

Following work by **DISC** with partners in Derry connected to the 400th anniversary of the city walls, the activities and the 3D-ICONS project were reported in several national newspapers in Ireland and also in the UK’s Sunday Times.

- <http://www.derryjournal.com/news/local-news/derry-s-walls-go-digital-1-4948848>
- <http://www.londonderrysentinel.co.uk/news/digital-scanning-of-largest-monument-for-400th-birthday-1-4953236>
- <http://www.belfasttelegraph.co.uk/news/local-national/northern-ireland/see-derrys-walls-in-a-new-dimension-famous-landmark-being-mapped-in-3d-29167859.html>
- A ¾ page article by DISC in the Sunday Times national newspaper describing the 3D-Icons Project has provided national coverage for the project and Europeana in the UK.

- <http://www.3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/In-the-news>

Report on 3D-ICONS project and CETIs digitisation activities in Greek newspaper 'Δημοκρατία Βορείου Ελλάδος' (Democracy Northern Greece), Issue 241(647) Monday 18 February 2013, pp 36

Franco Niccolucci chaired a session on "3D survey, modeling and monitoring" at Built Heritage 2013 in Milan, 18-20 November 2013 (<http://www.bh2013.polimi.it/>) at which several partners presented papers.

Visual Dimension has started a blog about its work on visualisation of the Benedictine abbey at Ename.

NTUA has disseminated about Europeana and the 3D-ICONS project through its collaboration at national level in Greece including with the 'Reviving the Ancient Agora in Athens' project of the American School of Classical Studies in Athens and the 'Digitisation and Promotion of the Archaeological Findings in Greece' project of the Archaeological Society at Athens.

8. Monitoring and evaluation

The project dissemination plan identified a series of success indicators that we planned to use to help evolve the dissemination strategy as the project progressed. This section of the report looks at those indicators and analyses the project’s dissemination activity over the first two years of the project.

8.1 Success indicators

The success indicators we identified included:

- Number of international events held
- Number of presentations at relevant conferences
- Number of publications in journal and similar media
- Project website: number of visitors to website
- Number of 3D-ICONS connected social networks and the number of members
- Email newsletters: Number of readers
- Liaisons & agreements with institutions / consortia not involved in project’s activities (formal and informal)

Targets

Description		Target Month 12	Target Month 24	Target Month 36	Actual month 24
International events held	No.	1	1	1	2+
Presentations at international events	No.	10	12	15	26+
Publications	No.	4	6	8	27
Project website	Visitors	7,000	10,000	15,000	12,929
3D-ICONS connected social networks	No.	2	3	4	9
Newsletters	Readers	100	150	300	+200 of which 111 direct + twitter & mailing lists
Liaisons and agreements	No	2	4	6	4

8.2 International events held

The project planned to hold an international workshop during each year of the project. By the end of month 24, project partners had organised the 2 planned workshops (at VAST 2012 and Digital Heritage 2013). In addition partners took part in an international workshop held during EuroMed 2012 and had delivered 3 training schools (Cyprus, Paestrum and Pontignano).

Sheena Bassett presenting at the 3D-ICONS workshop, VAST 2012

Participants at the 3D-ICONS workshop at Digital Heritage 2013

Participants at the Paestum summer school

8.3 Presentations at international conferences

The dissemination plan set a target of delivering 12 presentations at international conferences by month 24. This target has been exceeded with more than 26 presentations being given on the project or work being carried out in the framework of the project. Please note that where several partners have presented on the project in conference workshops this is counted as one for the sake of the monitoring target.

8.4 Publications

The dissemination plan set a relatively modest target of 6 project related publications by month 24. With more than 27 publications in conference proceedings and academic journals, the partners have excelled.

8.5 Project Website

MDR uses Google Analytics to track and analyse traffic to the 3D-ICONS website. Here is a summary of the traffic during the period from 1st February 2012 to 6th January 2014:

- Visits to the website were reported from 138 countries
- 12,929 visits were received from 1 February 2012 to 6 January 2014 (all unique visits) exceeding the target of 10,000 visits set in the dissemination plan.
- 78% were new visitors with 22% returning visitors
- 36,021 pages have been viewed since the start of the project with an average of 2.79 pages per visit and a 63% bounce rate. This represents a 200% growth in page views since 1st February 2013.

3D-ICONS website: visits by country

Analysis of visits to the website show a gradual increase with a peak in the week of 8-14 September 2013.

Website visits by week

Website visits by month

Top referrals

The top 20 referrals to the website during the period were:

The top referral was an article in El País Andalucía, which was published on 14th September 2013 on “El patrimonio ibero se expande en 3D”. This resulted in 286 visits to the website (95% of which were new) with an average of 4.1 pages viewed per visit. The article is online: http://ccaa.elpais.com/ccaa/2013/09/05/andalucia/1378398178_073401.html

Facebook was the next most important referral, leading to 273 visits. 66% of Facebook visitors were new, which is below average suggesting that the Facebook users are following the site more regularly looking at news and new resources as these are published.

Seven of the top referrals are project partners’ websites.

The CARARE project website has also been an important referral leading to 100 visits (45% new visitors) largely to the 3D-ICONS documentation pages and to news.

Digital Heritage 2013, Facebook, Google and LinkedIn were all important in referring visitors to the website.

Top content

The top viewed content on the website was:

- home page: www.3dicons-project.eu, 10,753 visits
- about, 2663 visits
- news, 2525 visits
- resources, 2522 visits

- community, 1,598 visits
- /eng home page, 987 visits
- events, 786 visits
- consortium page, 648 visits
- user login, 449 visits
- other useful resources, 256 visits

Analysis of the top viewed content shows that while most visitors are going to the home page, the pages about the consortium, news, resources and community are also attracting visitors.

8.6 Social networks

The initial dissemination plan proposed that 3D-ICONS should establish a presence on Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Slideshare and YouTube but did not set targets for numbers of followers.

The monitoring figures are as follows:

Network	2012-14	Change since 1/2/2013
<p>Twitter twitter.com/#!/3dicons</p>	<p>Tweets: 262 Following: 162 Followers: 152 RT/favourites: 166 Mentions: 61</p>	<p>+ 218 + 96</p>
<p>Facebook http://www.facebook.com/groups/127358380732567/</p>	<p>Members: 82</p>	<p>+51 members</p>
<p>LinkedIn http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=2792030&trk=anet_ug_hm For LinkedIn our strategy has been to join the group established for CARARE.</p>	<p>Members: 598</p>	<p>+563*</p>
<p>YouTube http://www.youtube.com/user/3DIconsProject?feature=watch</p>	<p>Subscribers: 2 Videos: 5 Video views: 257</p>	<p>+1 + 149 views</p>
<p>Slideshare http://www.slideshare.net/3dicons</p>	<p>Followers: 1 SlideShares: 5 Views: 798</p>	<p>+1 + 798</p>

Connected social networks

The initial dissemination plan set a target of 3 connected social networks by month 24. Amongst others we are following (and are followed by) these networks in Twitter:

- **Digital Heritage 2013**
- **CyArk**
- **Smithsonian 3D**
- **V-MUST**
- **MeSch Project**
- **Ariadne Network**
- **Partarge Plus**
- **Scottish Ten**
- **Europeana**

8.7 Newsletter distribution

The project dissemination plan set a target of 150 readers of the project newsletter by month 24. The newsletter is distributed directly via the Mailchimp service to subscribers (people who have registered their interest in receiving the newsletter on the project website) and indirectly via notices on Twitter and the mailing lists. We estimate that by month 24 the project newsletter is being read by more than 200 people.

The Mailchimp service provides tools which allows us to analyse the direct distribution of the newsletter. The statistics Issue 4 of the newsletter was sent to 111 registered recipients, the analytics provided by Mailchimp show that the newsletter had:

- An opening rate of 32.2% (the industry average is 23.5%)
- A click rate of 12.6% (the industry average is 2.9%)

The top links clicked by readers were:

- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/FBK>
- <http://www.museumsandheritage.com/show/>
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/News-from-Paestum>
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Skellig-Michael>
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/Events/CHNT-2013>

Top locations by opens

	USA	9 20.5%
	Belgium	6 13.6%
	France	6 13.6%
	United Kingdom	5 11.4%
	Italy	5 11.4%

The indirect distribution can be interpreted using the website statistics, which show that the newsletter and news items are consistently amongst the top viewed content. For example:

- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News> has had 2,550 page views
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Digitization-of-Saint-Michel-de-Cuxa> has had 210 page views with an average of 2.26 minutes spent on the page
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/Newsletter/Issue-3> has had 172 page views with an average of 1.35 minutes spent on the page
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/News-from-Paestum> had 84 page views with an average of 1.05 minutes spent on the page
- <http://3dicons-project.eu/eng/News/CAAI-presents-first-results> had 83 page views

Analysis of the statistics suggest that readership of the newsletter is on target, with analysis of the website statistics showing that recipients of the newsletter and notices on Twitter and Facebook are interested and follow the links to read the full news story published on the project website.

8.8 Liaisons and agreements

The initial dissemination plan set a target of establishing 4 liaisons and agreements with institutions or consortia by month 24. Currently the project has signed, or is in the process of signing, external partner agreements with 5 organisations:

<http://www.uniss.it/youniss/> - ARSLAB at the University of Sassari based in Sardinia, contacted the project as a result of CYI-STARC modelling the Holy Well of St Cristina in Sardinia and are interested in the digitisation pipeline. (Signed)

<http://archive.cyark.org> – contacted the project as they are keen to expose their 3D models through Europeana. (Signed)

<http://www.groma20.com/> - who contacted the project via Facebook and has offered some very interesting content from Spain (Merida) which it is keen to make accessible via Europeana. (Signed)

<http://www.dainst.org/en/> - contacted the project to learn more about the CARARE2 metadata schema for documenting 3D models produced by DAI's different departments and locations. DAI sees visibility of its content in Europeana as an added bonus. (In process)

3D-ICONS partners have signed Data Exchange Agreements with Europeana, which has additionally been signed by the Archaeological Museum of Milan (a partner of Polimi).

9. Conclusion

This interim dissemination report presents our dissemination strategy for 2014 and reports on dissemination activities in years one and two of the 3D-ICONS project.

In the first year of the project dissemination activities focussed on raising awareness about the project in national and international contexts, and establishing the basic set of dissemination materials. In year two, dissemination activities focussed on presenting digitisation and other work in progress and project results, and on developing and extending the network of contacts.

Monitoring of dissemination activity shows that the project partners are meeting and exceeding the dissemination targets that were set at the start of the project. It is pleasing to note the continuing interest in the project's digitisation and other activities by the stakeholder community.

During the final year of the project, work will commence to deliver content to Europeana and on the preparation of guidelines for best practices in the production of 3D for cultural heritage monuments. Thus the focus of dissemination activities will be on presenting the project's achievements culminating in the final project event, which will take place in late autumn 2014.

10. References

- [1] Annex I – “Description of Work”-DoW
- [2] Deliverable 8.1, “Initial Dissemination Plan”

11. Appendix I: Twitter Guidelines

Guidelines for Tweeting About the 3D-ICONS Project

KMKG and MDR are managing the Twitter account of the 3D-ICONS project (@3DICONs).

The 3D-ICONS project members are invited to Tweet about the project or retweet any tweets of interest.

In order to make the best use of Twitter for the Project the following guidelines will be of help:

1. Target audience –The prime focus should be people from Cultural Heritage organisations/institutions. After this, it should be aimed at professionals (not necessary working in the field on Cultural Heritage) and subjects in the field of education. In general, the community we intend to target is Europeana and the digital libraries community, cultural heritage and industry end-user organisations, publishers, online hosts, academic institutions, SMEs.

2. Objectives for Twitter:

- a. Keep key followers informed of 3D-ICONS activities (progress made, publications, upcoming events etc.)
- b. Inform followers about topics/issues of interest that are related to 3D-ICONS, namely 3D digitisation of the Cultural Heritage.

3. Achieving the objectives:

- a. Informing followers about new content on the 3D-ICONS website, Facebook and LinkedIn.
- b. Informing followers about topics/issues of interest that are related to 3D-ICONS (i.e. upcoming conferences/prizes/info days/calls/research areas/innovations/studies)

4. Tweets posted: Twitter only allows tweets of 140 characters or less, tweets should include a link with a title (to effectively communicate the message) and in some cases use a more confidential tone.

5. 3D-ICONS follows – people who are related to the target audience and professionally involved in 3D digitisation. We do not follow people whose tweets are of a personal nature. We will periodically review and 'unfollow' the less useful tweeters to make monitoring the feeds more manageable.

6. Tweeting: it would be useful to Tweet at least once a fortnight

7. Reply: The 3D-ICONS account will reply to specific tweets directed at @3DICONs (asking questions or feedback about the project).

3D-ICONS Project members (and followers):

- remember to use the hash tag when you are tweeting about the project: #3DICONs
- Please Retweet any tweets that may of interest to your friends and colleagues